

The rationale for opting for cement-based materials as an engineered barrier in a geological disposal facility for radioactive waste

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Abstract

This paper provides experimental justification for selecting cement-based materials for engineered safety barriers (ESB) in geological disposal facilities (GDF) for radioactive waste. The long-term performance of three materials — Ordinary Portland Cement Concrete (OPCC), Calcium Aluminate Cement Concrete (CACC), and Nirex Reference Vault Backfill (NRVB) — was comparatively analyzed under conditions simulating groundwater impact in a crystalline rock massif. A one-year filtration experiment was conducted using synthetic groundwater at elevated pressure. The evaluation included comprehensive assessment of phase composition evolution, mechanical strength, hydraulic permeability, and chemical/electrochemical parameters of the interacting liquid phase. Results demonstrated that OPCC maintained increased content of strengthening phases (C-S-H, ettringite), enhanced mechanical strength exceeding the required minimum of 7.5 MPa, and consistently low hydraulic permeability ($\sim 10^{-12}$ m/s), meeting ESB criteria for contact with bentonite buffer. The pH of its filtrate remained below 11.5, minimizing alkaline degradation risks for bentonite. In contrast, NRVB exhibited complete dissolution of C-S-H and portlandite, resulting in significant strength reduction and high hydraulic permeability, making it unsuitable for bentonite buffer contact. For aluminate concrete, cross-reaction of metastable phase CAH_{10} into less dense C_3AH_6 caused substantial strength decrease and increased hydraulic permeability exceeding maximum permissible values (10^{-10} m/s), limiting its GDF application. Based on these findings, Ordinary Portland Cement Concrete emerges as the preferred material for ESB construction in GDF. These results establish foundation for subsequent geochemical modeling of long-term cement barrier evolution.

Keywords

Concrete, Radioactive waste, Geological disposal facility, Engineered barrier, Compressive strength, Hydraulic permeability, Phase composition

Introduction

The operation of nuclear power plants, despite the obvious advantages in the form of environmentally friendly

electricity, is accompanied by a very pressing problem — the generation and subsequent management of radioactive waste (RW) (Lokonova et al. 2025). At the international level, the long-term management of high-level

radioactive waste (HLW) is based on the concept of deep geological disposal, which is widely recognized as the most reliable strategy for ensuring the isolation of radionuclides from the biosphere over geological timescales. The development of such systems is closely associated with large-scale underground research programs and site characterization campaigns, such as the Beishan Underground Research Laboratory in China, which integrates in situ experiments and safety-relevant testing for geological disposal concepts (Wang et al. 2018).

Within this framework, understanding radionuclide behavior in deep geological environments is essential for safety assessment of disposal systems. Recent studies on radionuclide migration and speciation in crystalline rock systems have demonstrated the complexity of coupled hydrogeochemical and transport processes controlling radionuclide mobility, including uranium and selenium in fractured granite environments (Wu et al. 2024; Duan et al. 2025; Duan et al. 2026; Wu et al. 2026). These findings further emphasize the necessity of robust engineered barrier systems capable of limiting radionuclide release.

RW of classes 1 and 2 (high-level (HLW) and intermediate-level waste (ILW) containing long-lived radionuclides (State Duma of the Russian Federation 2011; Government of the Russian Federation 2022)) must be finally isolated in stable geological formations at a depth of several hundred meters in accordance with national regulatory requirements (Federal service for environmental, technological and nuclear supervision 2018). In deep geological repository (DGR)/geological disposal facility (GDF) concepts, long-term safety is ensured by a multi-barrier system, which includes the waste form, engineered barriers, and the surrounding geological environment.

One of the key components of engineered safety barriers (ESB) is cement-based materials, which are widely applied in DGR/GDF designs (Tyupina et al. 2023). Their use is motivated by their chemical buffering capacity, low cost, and ability to tailor physico-chemical properties through additives. Cement-based materials are employed both as structural elements and as part of the engineered barrier system (EBS), contributing to mechanical stability and geochemical control of near-field conditions. Recent advances in engineered barrier design further highlight their role in controlling radionuclide migration and long-term safety performance of disposal systems (Li et al. 2025).

In addition, cement-based materials are used as immobilization matrices for intermediate-level waste (ILW) containing short-lived radionuclides (Kozlov and Gorbunova 2011; Tyupina et al. 2016), and in some disposal concepts also for long-lived radionuclide-bearing waste (Tsebakovskaya et al. 2015; Kamorny et al. 2021; Tyupina et al. 2023). Recent developments in engineered barrier research further emphasize the interactions between cementitious materials and bentonite-based buffer systems, which are central to most repository designs (Li et al. 2026).

The safety functions of cement-based materials in GDF/DGR systems include (Karnland et al. 2007; Gupalo 2009; García Calvo et al. 2010; Ye et al. 2014; Bao et

al. 2016; Posiva SKB 2017; Vasconcelos et al. 2018; Sun et al. 2020):

- High mechanical strength;
- Chemical containment through the formation of highly alkaline porewater;
- Low hydraulic conductivity.

Within the multi-barrier system, cement-based structures also play an indirect role in ensuring the long-term performance of bentonite buffer materials, which are widely used due to their swelling capacity, low permeability, and high sorption potential for radionuclides (Tuchkova et al. 2012; Tsebakovskaya et al. 2015; Pryadko et al. 2020; Morozov et al. 2022; Krupskaya et al. 2023). However, the interaction between cement porewater and bentonite remains a critical issue. Highly alkaline conditions ($\text{pH} \geq 12$) may lead to progressive alteration of smectite phases, which are responsible for the key sealing and sorption properties of bentonite (Karnland et al. 2007; Ye et al. 2014; Bao et al. 2016; Sun et al. 2020).

Therefore, the aim of this work is to substantiate the choice of the composition of cement-based materials as ESB in the GDF for RW from the point of view of changes in mechanical strength, hydraulic permeability, phase composition, chemical composition and electrochemical characteristics of groundwater based on the results of a long-term model experiment and to obtain a set of data for subsequent modeling of the evolution of characteristics that determine safety functions throughout the entire period of operation of the geological facility for radioactive waste. In fact, this work in the Russian Federation is in many ways pioneering.

Material and methods

Ordinary Portland Cement Concrete (OPCC), Nirex Reference Vault Backfill (NRVB), and Calcium Aluminate Cement Concrete (CACC) samples were used as cement-based materials for the studies. Samples were prepared by mixing the components in the mass ratios presented in Table 1 (Allard et al. 1984; Rochelle et al. 2014; Bogatov 2018; Vasconcelos et al. 2018; Safonov and Boldyrev 2019) followed by their plastic molding and curing for 28 days in a desiccator at a relative air humidity of ~95%.

The initial data were obtained using rectangular prism-shaped samples measuring $3 \times 1 \times 1$ cm. To conduct the model experiment, cylindrical samples with a diameter of 47 mm and a height of 31 mm were made on the laboratory setup, the schematic diagram of which is shown in Fig. 1. The samples were sealed inside the housing of a stainless steel filtration cell, a photograph of which is shown in Fig. 2, using epoxy resin to eliminate the influence of the near-wall effect on the experimental results. The operating principle of the laboratory setup is based on the filtration of a Yeniseisky subsoil area site synthetic groundwater, selected as the site for the construction of the GDF in Russia, under

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the laboratory setup for conducting a model experiment.

Figure 2. Photograph of a cell for conducting a model experiment with samples of the cement-based materials being studied.

a pressure of 1 MPa, used previously in (González-Santamaría et al. 2020), pumped with high-purity nitrogen (99.9999%). The pressure and temperature of the aqueous medium were recorded using a digital temperature sensor and an excess pressure sensor with a 0–5 V signal (Kozlov and Tyupina 2023; Tyupina et al. 2025a, 2025b).

Cylindrical cement-based materials samples for analysis of changes in composition and microstructure after exposure to a synthetic groundwater from the Yeniseisky site, the composition of which is presented in Table 2 and was obtained on the basis of literature (Rozov et al. 2018; Morozov et al. 2022), were removed from the housing of the filter cells using a laboratory manual hydraulic press Carver 3851-0 due to their strong fixation with epoxy resin.

After removing the cylindrical samples from the cell bodies for further study of their property evolution, they were cut into rectangular prisms measuring $3 \times 1 \times 1$ cm using a diamond disc on a stone-cutting machine. Sampling was performed relative to the sample face, through which synthetic groundwater was injected at distances of 0–1, 1–2, and 2–3 cm for further study of changes in strength characteristics, phase composition, and microstructure, as shown in Fig. 3.

Table 1. Composition of mixtures for the production of cement-based materials samples

Type of material	Component	Content, wt. %
Ordinary Portland Cement Concrete (OPCC)	Cement CEM I 52.5N, wt. %	30.50
	Quartz sand	49.50
	Distilled water	20.00
Nirex Reference Vault Backfill (NRVB)	Cement CEM I 52.5N	26.00
	CaCO ₃	29.00
	Ca(OH) ₂	10.00
	Distilled water	35.00
Calcium Aluminate Cement Concrete (CACC)	Calcium Aluminate Cement GC-35 50	42.97
	Quartz sand	42.97
	Plasticizer S-3	0.30
	Distilled water	13.76

Table 2. Composition and pH of the synthetic and real groundwater from the Yeniseisky site of the Nizhne-Kansky crystalline rock massif

Concentration, $\mu\text{g} \times \text{L}^{-1}$								pH
Ca ²⁺	K ⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺	CO ₃ ²⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	HCO ₃ ⁻	Cl ⁻	
Synthetic groundwater								
71943	6647	17701	28870	–	47413	–	–	7.23
Groundwater from Yeniseisky site (Rozov et al. 2018)								
48497	4497	12009	32186	5701	15561	200756	25311	7.50

The mineral composition of cement-based materials was determined using an X-ray diffractometer Rigaku Ultima-IV with a copper anode. Mineral phase identification was performed using MDI software Jade 6 using the PDF -2 database, and the calculation of their quantitative content using the Rietveld method in Profex software for BGMN (Doebelin and Kleeberg 2015; Post and Bish 2018). The content of amorphous C-S-H gel was determined by introducing 10% CeO₂ into the sample as an internal standard (Scrivener et al. 2016).

Carl Zeiss LEO1450VP scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to study the microstructure of

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the division of a cylindrical cement-based material sample to study the evolution of its characteristics as a result of a filtration experiment lasting 1 year.

cement-based materials samples. To remove the accumulated electrical charge, the sample was sputter-coated with gold in a vacuum chamber before imaging. The conductive coating layer thickness was 5–10 nm.

Compressive strength was determined using $3 \times 1 \times 1$ cm specimens using a PRG-1-5 manual hydraulic press. Compressive strength was calculated using equation (1).

$$\sigma_{comp.} = \frac{N}{S}, \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma_{comp.}$ is the compressive strength, MPa; N is the ultimate load at which the specimen fails, N; S is the area of the loaded face of the specimen, m^2 .

The pH of aqueous solutions in this study was determined using an IT-1101 pH meter with an ESK-10307 combined electrode. Eh was determined using an I-160MI laboratory ion meter equipped with an ERP-105 combined redox electrode and a TDL-1000-06 temperature sensor.

A Supec 7000 inductively coupled plasma ionization mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) was used for determination of the chemical elements concentration in aqueous phase samples. To calculate element concentrations, a series of calibration solutions prepared from the ICP-MS-68A standard solution were used in the concentration range of 0.03–10 ppb.

The hydraulic permeability of the cement-based materials samples under study was determined on a laboratory setup (Fig. 1) by calculation according to Darcy's law (2):

$$k = \frac{\Delta Q \times L}{A \times h \times \Delta t}, \quad (2)$$

where k is the hydraulic permeability, m/s; ΔQ is the flow of the synthetic groundwater at the outlet of the cell, m^3 ; L is the length of the sample, m; A is the cross-sectional area of the sample, m^2 ; Δt is the time interval ($t_1 - t_2$) during which the flow ΔQ was measured, s; t_1 is the start time of the hydraulic permeability determination, date: h:min:s; t_2 is the end time of the hydraulic permeability determination, date: h:min:s; h is the pressure drop of the synthetic groundwater at the ends of the sample, m.

The pressure drop of the synthetic groundwater was calculated based on the arithmetic mean of the pressure values at the inlet of the sample (P , MPa), recorded over time Δt in accordance with formula (3).

$$h = \frac{P}{\rho \times g}, \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the density of the synthetic groundwater, taken as 1000 kg/m^3 due to low mineralization; g is the acceleration due to gravity, $9.81 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$.

Hydraulic permeability at a standard temperature of 20°C k_{20} (m/s) was determined using formula (4):

$$k_{20} = 2.2902 \times \frac{(0.9842^T) \times k}{T^{0.1702}}, \quad (4)$$

where T is the average temperature obtained during the test according to the data recorded by the sensor, $^\circ\text{C}$.

Results and discussion

Changes in the phase composition of the studied cement-based materials as the results of a model experiment

The results of the quantitative X-ray diffraction analysis of the studied cement-based materials, obtained for the initial samples and those modified during the filtration experiment lasting 1 year, are presented in Table 3 and are listed according to the sampling scheme shown in Fig. 3: **0–1 cm**, **1–2 cm** and **2–3 cm** relative to the synthetic groundwater inlet.

X-ray diffraction patterns obtained during the analysis of the studied samples are shown in Figs 4–6.

Based on the results of quantitative X-ray diffraction analysis (Fig. 4) of Ordinary Portland Cement Concrete samples, it was found that filtration of a synthetic groundwater solution for one year leads to a 1.1- to 1.5-fold increase in the C-S-H content uniformly relative to the boundary of the synthetic groundwater inlet into the cell. This is due to the gradual hydration of $\beta\text{-C}_2\text{S}$ and should positively impact the mechanical strength of the sample. A 1.1-fold increase in calcite content was detected at the boundary of the model solution inlet into the Ordinary Portland Cement Concrete cell, while this effect is insignificant in other segments of the sample, due to the transformation of portlandite under the influence of the synthetic groundwater solution. The increase in portlandite

Table 3. Results of quantitative X-ray diffraction analysis

Material Phase	OPCC				NRVB				CACC			
	init*	0–1 cm	1–2 cm	2–3 cm	init.	0–1 cm	1–2 cm	2–3 cm	init.	0–1 cm	1–2 cm	2–3 cm
C ₄ AF	—	—	—	—	2.4	1.2	1.7	1.7	—	—	—	—
CAH ₁₀	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	6.6	0.7	0.8	1.1
C-S-H	7.4	8.4	9.1	10.8	2.3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Mg-chromite	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.7	1.4	0.8	1.5
α-C ₂ S	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.9	0.7	1.0	0.9
α-C ₂ SH	1.9	2.9	1.7	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
β-C ₂ S	5.7	3.9	10.7	2.1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Brucite	—	—	—	—	—	0.8	0.2	1.5	—	2.2	1.1	1.9
Hydrocalumite	2.6	1.0	1.6	1.1	2.1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Dolomite	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.5	—	—	—	—	—
Gismondine	5.0	1.4	2.0	1.6	—	—	—	—	6.6	4.1	5.9	4.1
Calcite	10.7	11.8	6.8	9.6	74.2	94.3	94	87.5	1.4	5.9	0.7	0.3
Katoite	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.5	6.6	9.2	10.4
Quartz	51.3	52.6	52.2	53.1	—	1.6	2.4	3.8	43.3	44.1	43.5	43.8
Monocarbonate	5.7	3.3	2.0	2.9	5.7	1.5	1.1	1.6	3.3	1.5	1.4	1.5
Mullite	—	—	—	—	0.2	0.6	0.1	1.8	—	—	—	—
Periclase	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.3	0.8	0.8	0.4
Portlandite	6.9	10.6	10.1	12.8	10.8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Thenardite	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.5
Spinel	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	34.9	31.8	34.2	33.6
Ettringite	2.6	4.1	3.8	5.9	2.3	—	—	2.1	—	—	—	—

* obtained for the initial sample.

Figure 4. X-ray diffraction patterns of the OPCC samples before and after the experiment.

content in the OPCC is caused by the prolonged hydration of unreacted Portland cement particles during sample manufacture. During the analysis of the obtained results, an increase in the ettringite content by 1.5–2.3 times relative to the content in the original samples was established, which should lead to pore clogging and have a positive

effect on the mechanical strength of the sample. The obtained results can be considered reliable, since the differences in composition exceed the value of 0.5% by weight, which is the minimum distinguishable amount when using the method for calculating the quantitative phase composition given in the paper.

Figure 5. X-ray diffraction patterns of the NRVB samples before and after the experiment.

Figure 6. X-ray diffraction patterns of the CACC samples before and after the experiment.

A study of the phase composition of NRVB revealed complete dissolution of C-S-H (Fig. 5, Table 3). This phenomenon results in the presence of a small amount of quartz in the sample obtained after one year of exposure to a synthetic groundwater and should also lead to a significant reduction in the mechanical strength of this material compared to the initial results. A lack of

portlandite and an increase in the mass fraction of calcite were also detected, caused by the partial carbonation of portlandite and its dissolution under the influence of the model groundwater solution. Ettringite was detected in virtually its original quantities only in the upper segment of the NRVB sample, which was least exposed to the synthetic groundwater.

A study of changes in the phase composition of CACC revealed a nearly fourfold increase in the mass fraction of calcite at the boundary of the synthetic groundwater inlet into the sample (Fig. 6, Table 3). This may be due to calcium leaching from the CACC components followed by precipitation of calcite due to the carbonate content of the synthetic groundwater. The increase in the katoite content in the sample, as determined by the filtration experiment, is a consequence of the slow recrystallization of metastable CAH_{10} (García Calvo et al. 2013) into a more thermodynamically stable phase, a typical phenomenon for aluminates phases in concrete, leading to a decrease in the mechanical strength of the material.

Figure 7. Profile of changes in mechanical strength of the cement-based materials samples under study as a result of the model experiment.

Changes in mechanical strength based on the results of a model experiment

The results of determining the strength characteristics of the cement-based materials samples under study are presented in Fig. 7. The tests were conducted on a sample of three samples, and the confidence interval was calculated as the standard deviation according to the Student's t-distribution. The resulting confidence interval values are added to the diagram (Fig. 7) as error bars.

Based on the mechanical test results, it was established that OPCC exposed to synthetic groundwater representative of the Yeniseisky site exhibited increased strength characteristics. This strengthening effect is attributed to filtration-induced mineralogical changes in the material. In particular, the increase in the content of the C-S-H phase and ettringite contributed to the observed improvement in mechanical properties. Microphotographs of significant clusters of needle-shaped crystals filling the pores of OPCC sample are shown in Fig. 8A and Fig. 8B. These crystals have a hexagonal prism morphology and contain a relatively high amount of sulfur, as revealed by SEM-EDS (Fig. 8C). This fact further confirms the presence of ettringite in the studied samples, and its filling of the pore space causes an increase in strength properties.

Based on the obtained mechanical strength values, OPCC was found to meet the requirements established for cement-based materials in GDF/DGR applications (Posiva SKB 2017). The measured strength exceeds the minimum required value of 7.5 MPa (Fig. 7). In addition, this material

Figure 8. SEM images of ettringite accumulation in the pores of OPCC sample at magnifications of X1000 (A) and X5000 (B), as well as the EDS spectrum obtained as a result of microprobe analysis of the detected crystals (C).

is capable of withstanding the potential loads associated with bentonite buffer swelling (2.5 MPa) and groundwater hydrostatic pressure (5 MPa) (Posiva SKB 2017).

The strength characteristics of NRVB show a significant decrease as a result of filtration of a synthetic groundwater from the Yeniseisky site for a period of 1 year. When creating lining in a tunnel/borehole in contact with a compacted bentonite buffer, this material will be ineffective due to its strength below the possible maximum loads in the GDF of 7.5 MPa (Posiva SKB 2017).

For the CACC sample, a significant decrease in strength by a factor of 2.2–3.3 was observed (Fig. 7). This phenomenon is associated with a significant drop in the content of metastable CAH_{10} , which undergoes recrystallization to C_3AH_6 (Fig. 6), which has a lower density.

Figure 9. Change in the hydraulic permeability of the studied cement-based materials during the experiment lasting 1 year.

Moreover, only the upper section of the specimen demonstrated a strength that slightly exceeded the established SKB criterion of 7.5 MPa (Posiva SKB 2017). This fact suggests that aluminate concrete cannot be used as an ESB material in GDF, as it is incapable of withstanding the predicted maximum loads.

Changes in hydraulic permeability values during the model experiment

The results of determining the hydraulic conductivity of the cement-based materials samples studied in the study are presented in Fig. 9, which shows that:

- Ordinary Portland Cement Concrete, during a 1-year filtration experiment, retains hydraulic conductivity values significantly lower (approximately 10^{-12} m/s) than the upper permissible limit of 10^{-10} m/s (García Calvo et al. 2010), which allows its use in GDF;
- the hydraulic permeability values of CACC and NRVB exceed the regulated maximum of 10^{-10} m/s to varying degrees, which makes the use of these materials in GDF impossible.

Changes in pH, Eh and chemical composition of liquid phase samples at the outlet of the filtration cell during a model experiment

Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 present the results of electrochemical analyses and compositional characterization of synthetic groundwater filtrates from the Yeniseisky site after

Figure 10. Concentrations of analyzed ions in aqueous phase samples at the outlet of the cells relative to the filtered pore volumes of synthetic groundwater.

Figure 11. Graphical dependences of pH and Eh of the filtrate of a synthetic groundwater on the time of the experiment, obtained during a model experiment lasting 1 year.

passage through the studied cement-based material samples during the 1-year experiment.

During the experiment, the pH of synthetic groundwater filtrates passing through OPCC and CACC samples did not exceed 11.5. These values indicate that both materials can be used in direct contact with bentonite. Previous studies have shown that the detrimental effects of alkaline environments on bentonite begin at pH 12.4 and above (García Calvo et al. 2010). These effects become more pronounced at elevated temperatures. When studying aqueous phase samples obtained at the outlet of the filtration cells, it was determined that the synthetic groundwater, when in contact with the cement-based materials samples, maintained an oxidizing environment characterized by values no higher than 350 mV. For OPCC, a short-term reduction environment (down to -50 mV) was observed in the synthetic groundwater on days 58 and 84 of the experiment.

Changes in pH and Eh in filtrate samples collected from cells containing the test cement-based materials (Fig. 11) are primarily due to changes in the concentration of potassium and sodium ions (Fig. 10) in the solution. However, the dependence of pH on the concentration of potassium and sodium cations is less pronounced, as this parameter is sensitive to changes in concentrations by an order of magnitude. The most dramatic changes in pH and Eh in filtrate samples from NRVB and CACC samples are achieved over a relatively short period of time. The least intense dynamics of pH and Eh evolution in filtrate samples of synthetic groundwater were observed for OPCC. These phenomena are due to differences in the hydraulic permeability of the test materials, which determines the rate of dissolution of alkaline components from the pore space of the concrete.

During the interaction of aluminate concrete with a synthetic groundwater solution, a dependence of pH and Eh of the medium on the total concentration of K^+ and Na^+ is also observed (Fig. 10 and Fig. 11). A decrease in the concentration of potassium, sodium and calcium on the 28th day of the experiment leads to the pH of the medium reaching values of about 7–9, which determines the main contribution

of these cations to the alkalization of the liquid phase samples of the selected filtrates of the synthetic groundwater.

Conclusions

The study results showed that Ordinary Portland Cement Concrete is the most suitable for use in the GDF of the cement-based materials studied in this study, as it meets all the required safety functions, including after exposure to a synthetic groundwater: it exhibits high mechanical strength ($\sigma = 29.1\text{--}44.0$ MPa), low water permeability ($k_{20} \sim 10^{-12}$ m/s), and acceptable pH values in the filtrate (pH < 11.5), which do not pose a significant threat to the insulating properties of the bentonite buffer layer.

The results of this experiment can also be used to calibrate and test a computational model for the evolution of Ordinary Portland Cement Concrete characteristics under the influence of groundwater using the PHREEQC 3.7.3 computational code. This modeling will allow for an assessment of the long-term ability of Ordinary Portland Cement Concrete as an ESB material to maintain its properties necessary for performing safety functions throughout the entire operational life of a Geological Disposal Facility for radioactive waste.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.